
rapprochement of the Azerbaijani and Turkish people against spread of the ideas of Pan-Turkizm which overtook then the Ottoman Empire and some Muslim people of the Russian Empire. The Turkish factor was due in no small part to establishing of the Azerbaijani nationhood as in 1918, and in the 1990s. Meanwhile interest of Turks in elimination of ADR in 1920, unwillingness of Turkey to be involved in a full-scale war on the side of Azerbaijan in war for Karabakh in 1991–1993, the situation around the Zurich protocols of 2009, non-recognition of TRSK by Azerbaijan, existence of other disagreements on international issues between Baku and Ankara show, that both parties first of all are guided by own interests and existing foreign policy condition, but not an aspiration to correspond always and in all ways to the above-mentioned principle “One nation – two states.”

ELENA DMITRIEVA. IMAGE OF RUSSIA IN KAZAKHSTAN AND IMAGE OF KAZAKHSTAN IN RUSSIA: AS WE SEE EACH OTHER // *The review was written for the bulletin “Russia and the Moslem World.”*

Keywords: Russia, Kazakhstan, factors of formation of social perceptions, historical-cultural context, stereotypes, integration, image of country.

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Introduction: The study of problems concerning the perception of an image of one or another country becomes ever more important in the modern world. The security of countries, their welfare and place on a political or economic map of the world largely depend on the development of their relations between themselves, and especially relations with neighboring

countries. Many states which devote much attention to the important problem of forming a positive image of their country spend large means for the purpose. The perception of the inhabitants of the two neighboring countries – Russia and Kazakhstan – is influenced by quite a few factors: among them traditional customs and habits and social-cultural ties between the people of the two countries play an important role.

Perception of Image of Kazakhstan by People of Russia. Scholars V. Kolosov and Zh. Tokbulatova in their work “The Image of Kazakhstan in Russia in the Mirror of Public Opinion” analyze the perception of Kazakhstan, which has taken shape in Russian society on the basis of public opinion polls carried out in the period between 1993 and 2017 by several sociological agencies. Russia has one of the world’s longest land borders with Kazakhstan, a common historical past and supposed future. By the poll results Kazakhstan is in the category of the most important potential partners of Russia, but has never taken the central place among them. Most Russians note the importance of the development of the economic ties with Kazakhstan, but at the same time, in their view, their spheres are few and far between.*

Kazakhstan looks a reliable partner in Russian public opinion. Stereotypes concerning Kazakhstan as a former Soviet republic are gradually disappearing. Although certain cultural and economic associations are now seldom mentioned, and the role of old notions, subjects and persons is not mentioned any longer, the subject of integration is gradually taking more important place in public opinion polls. This includes various questions – from the setting up of common borders to the creation of joint integration ventures with Kazakhstan.

* V. Kolosov, Zh. Tokbulatova. *Obraz Kazakhstana v Rossii v zerkale obshchestvennogo mneniya* [The Image of Kazakshtan in Russia in the Mirror of Public Opinion] // “*Regionalniye issledovaniya,*” Smolensk, 2018, № 2, pp. 58–67.

Kazakhstan is culturally closer and friendlier to Russia than other post-Soviet republics. However, a shortage of visible common aspects of development in the economic sphere between the two countries does not allow Kazakhstan to enter the circle of promising partners of Russia in the sphere of investments, technologies, scientific developments, etc., whereas the ideas of Russians about strategic allies and rivals are not stable and quickly react to changes in the current foreign-politic situation.

Citizens of Kazakhstan about Relations with Russia. The work entitled "What do Kazakhs Think of Their Relations with the Northern Neighbor?" by N. Kosmarskaya and I. Savin (Institute of Oriental Studies RAS) is devoted to factors forming the image of Russia in Kazakhstan.**

The article has the aim to show Russia to the Kazakh people as an economic resource, and also its role in the historical-cultural aspect. The article is based on field research of its authors in 2016 (on example of dwellers of the city of Petropavlovsk, North Kazakhstan), as well as on an analysis of the two leading Kazakhstan's newspapers in the Russian and Kazakh languages. We should mention that for Kazakhstan's citizens Russia is the friendliest country - 81 percent. In 2016 more than 40 percent of those polled welcomed economic and technical cooperation with Russia (in 2015 their number was 49 percent). The growing interest in receiving education in Russia is registered in Kazakhstan (32 percent for the second year running). Russian integration initiatives play an important role in the perception of Russia by Kazakhstan's citizens. (It should be noted that Kazakhs support only the economic variants of integration and show great caution toward other initiatives (joint currency, united army, common information area, etc., whereas Russians welcome any integrations). Kazakhstan continues to show a certain bent to the Russian information area

** N. Kosmarskaya, I. Sonin. *Chto dumayut kazakhstanbtsy ob otnosheniyakh s severnym sosedom?* [What Do Kazakhs Think of Their Relations with the Northern Neighbor?] // *Tsentralnaya Evraziya, Moscow, Institute of Oriental Sciences RAS, 2018, № 1, pp. 175-195.*

(69 percent of Kazakhs favored the setting up of a joint TV-radio company of the Eurasian Economic Corporation.

In the sphere of military-strategic partnership, however, there is another picture. In 2016, 34 percent of Kazakhstan's citizens believed that CIS countries threatened their country, whereas Russia was a subject of a possible military support – 59 percent. The European Union was not mentioned as such. However, in 2016 pro-European sentiments in Kazakhstan grew from two to 11 percent, having reached a five-year maximum.

About 24 percent of those polled in Kazakhstan regard a possibility of temporary work in Russia desirable for themselves, and 22 percent express interest in moving to any of the former Soviet republics and staying there.

As to an analysis of the press in the Russian and Kazakh languages, it should be noted that the bulk of information in Russian has a neutral or positive connotation, and some publications in the Kazakh language show that part of Kazakh citizens express concern with the position of Russia on the questions of economic cooperation with Eurasian countries, interaction with neighboring states, etc., and these tendencies persist in polls and questionnaires.

Conclusions. As we see, despite the evidently good relations between the people of Russia and Kazakhstan, there are signs that the situation is dynamic enough, which can lead to a change in priorities of the population of one country in relation to that of the neighboring country. A great significance for the formation of the image of Russia among Kazakhstan's citizens is played by ethnicity, although this factor is not decisive. For Russian citizens the most important issue is the living standard and economic indices in Kazakhstan in examining the problems of integration. A separate role is played by the influence of the mass media on the views of the respondents. An analysis of the perception of one another by citizens of Russia and Kazakhstan is a very important subject, inasmuch as this subject helps reveal a multitude of various factors influencing relations between the two countries.